

ClairCity: Citizen-led air pollution reduction in cities

D2.5 ClairCity Annual Conference – Poland

April 2018

Document Details

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Creation Date	23/04/2018
Date of Last Revision	30/04/2018
Description	<p>This report evidences the ClairCity Annual Conference 2018 (the actual deliverable (D2.5) is the conference).</p> <p>The ClairCity Annual Conference (open to the public) and Consortium Meeting (just for project partners and External Advisory Board members) took place on 25-27 April in Sosnowiec, Poland. The event was hosted by the consortium partner, Sosnowiec City Hall (SOS) at the Sosnowiec Science and Technology Park (Wojska Polskiego 8, 41-208 Sosnowiec) and was a 'success' in our assessment and judging from the external participants' feedback. Both the ClairCity Consortium Meeting and Annual Conference run smoothly, proofed that rapid progress is being made in all Work Packages.</p> <p>The report includes a detailed copy of the three-day programme (agenda), the attendance list, link to presentations and photos of the conference, and references to Public Relations around the conference. Participants of the conference are aware that their names and pictures may be used in ClairCity publications.</p>

Version History

Version	Updated By	Date	Changes / Comments
V1.0	Corra Boushel	April 2018	Initiating document
V2.0	Irati Artola	April 2018	Last edits

Contributions and Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the following people for their important contributions used in the preparation of this final document.

Native Language Check	Corra Boushel (UWE)
Project internal comments	-

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1 Introduction

The ClairCity Annual Conference (open to the public) and Consortium Meeting (just for project partners and External Advisory Board members) took place on 25-27 April in Sosnowiec, Poland. The event was hosted by the consortium partner, Sosnowiec City Hall (SOS) at the Sosnowiec Science and Technology Park (Wojska Polskiego 8, 41-208 Sosnowiec) and was a 'success' in our assessment and judging from the external participants' feedback.

The Annual Conference took place in Sosnowiec, Poland as an authorised change from our original intention of hosting the conference in Norway. This change was determined in relation to the benefits the project discovered of hosting in our pilot cities, to ensure strong and sustained relationships with each pilot city and buddy partner. Our experience hosting events in Bristol, Amsterdam and Ljubljana indicated a valuable benefit to this choice, which was also apparent in Sosnowiec.

This report summarises the activities of the ClairCity Annual Conference (open to the public) and Consortium Meeting (just for project partners and External Advisory Board members). These meetings took place on 25-27 April in Sosnowiec, Poland.

2 Overview of the meeting

Day 1 - Wednesday 25th April 2018 - ClairCity Annual Conference

This was the public part of the Consortium Meeting open to external people. Over 90 people took part in the Conference including Consortium Members, External Advisory Board and external participants including Mayors of Cities in the Silesian Region.

Given primarily heating is a problem for air quality in the Sosnowiec area and region, followed by transport, these issues were embraced as a general theme. Each annual conference has shifted its focus in this way, ensuring all parts of the project are scrutinised at the appropriate time over the course of the project. In Sosnowiec, Particulate Matter (PM) and policy actions in the Silesian Region as well as in other EU and non-EU cities were the main focus of the public conference.

Day 2 - Thursday 26th April 2018 – Internal Project Meeting I

Meeting for Consortium Members and External Advisory Board only.

This day was partly dedicated to the interaction with the ClairCity Cities / Regions through a semi-structured session, and partly to Work Packages (WP) specific discussions.

WP5 (Quantification) for example met with all the staff working on its various tasks; The Technical Director, the City partners and the staff behind the WP7 (Scenarios) also joined as the link between these tasks is crucial. Concrete timeframes and action plans were written down.

In a plenary session on WP4 (Engagement), ongoing and upcoming engagement activities (i.e. Promotion of the Game and App in cities and the preparation for filming, schools competition and city days) were discussed.

Day 3 - Friday 27th April 2018 – Internal Project Meeting II

Meeting for Consortium Members and External Advisory Board only.

This day was partly dedicated to the interaction with the ClairCity External Advisory Board, and partly to (plenary) Work Packages (WP) specific discussions.

References to Public Relations around the conference and pictures will be made are available on this page of the ClairCity website: <http://www.claircity.eu/2018/04/23/claircity-annual-conference-2018/>. Additionally some examples of the insights that have been shared on social media can be found on [Twitter](#) and [Facebook](#).

3 Programme

3.1 Agenda Wednesday, 25th April – ClairCity Public Meeting

Registration between 9:00 and 9:30

9.30 – 9.40	Opening	Hans Bolscher, Project Director
Sosnowiec and Poland: air quality situation and policies		
9.40 – 9.50	Introduction by the Mayor of Sosnowiec	Arkadiusz Chęciński
9.50 – 10.15	Air pollution, climate and health	Renata Złotkowska, Director of the Institute of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health in Sosnowiec
10.15 – 10.40	Role of citizens in air pollution advocacy – the Polish experience	Rafał Psik, Zagłębiowski Alarm Smogowy
10.40 – 11.10	<i>Coffee & tea break</i>	
Heating, transport and citizens		
11.10 – 11.30	Solid fuel use as a pollution source – local challenges	Adam Liwochowski, Head of Communal Management and Environment Department
11.30 – 11.50	Transport as a pollution source – local challenges	Robert Dworak, Head of the Road and Traffic Management Department
11.50 – 12.10	ClairCity Sosnowiec Policy Baseline Report	Stephan Slingerland, Trinomics
12.10 – 12.30	Q&A	
12.30 – 13.30	<i>Lunch break with posters on view</i>	
How ClairCity meets the challenge: Project demonstrations		
13.30 – 13.40	The ClairCity Process – bringing the evidence together	Enda Hayes, UWE
13.40 – 13.55	ClairCity Skylines Game	Enda Hayes, UWE
13.55 – 14.10	GreenANTS app	Mirjam Fredriksen, NILU
14.10 – 14.25	Delphi process and citizen voice	Jim Longhurst, UWE
14.25 – 14.40	Modelling “behavior” in heating and transport	Kris Vanherle, TML
14.40 – 15.00	Q&A	
15.00 – 15.15	<i>Short coffee & tea break</i>	
EU and international experience		
15.15 – 15.30	Pro-environmental behavioural change: Role of personalised information	Adnan Muhammad, iSCAPE Project
15.30 – 15.50	The (re)emerging problem of solid fuel use and PM emissions in Bristol and the UK	Andy Edwards, Bristol City Council

15.50 – 16.10	Residential Wood Combustion in Nordic Countries – The need for high resolution emission inventories	Susana Lopez-Aparicio, NILU
16.10 – 16.30	Air Pollution Management in Delhi National Capital Region	Mukesh Khare, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi
16.30 – 17.00	Q&A / Panel discussion	
17.00	Poster presentation session with networking	
17.30	Conference close	
	Dinner in Sosnowiec hosted by Sosnowiec's Mayor <i>Siedlisko Stawiki Restaurant, Sosnowiec, 5 Kresowa str</i>	

All presentations from the public conference will be made available on this page of the ClairCity website: <http://www.claircity.eu/2018/04/23/claircity-annual-conference-2018/>

3.2 Agenda Thursday, 26th April – ClairCity Internal Meeting Part 1

9.00	Opening of the day	
ClairCity Cities / Regions – Knowledge Exchange		
9.00 – 10.30	Interaction with the ClairCity city / region partners* <i>*see concept in Annex</i>	
10.30 – 11.00	<i>Coffee & tea break</i>	
11.00 – 12.00	Interaction with the ClairCity city / region partners* <i>*see concept in Annex</i>	
Work Packages time		
12.00 – 13.00	<i>WP Session – Detailed WP Discussions (to be arranged by WP leads)</i>	
13.00 – 14.00	<i>Lunch break</i>	
14.00 – 15.00	<i>WP Session – Detailed WP Discussions (to be arranged by WP leads)</i>	
15.00 – 15.30	<i>Coffee & tea break</i>	
15.30 – 17.30	WP4 Engagement (Eva Csobod and Laura Fogg Rogers to lead) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of the Game and App in cities • Preparation for filming, schools competition and city days 	<i>Partners not involved in WP4 may use this time for parallel meetings.</i> <i>Detailed WP Discussions (to be arranged by WP leads)</i>
17.30	Tour around the “Old Industrial Monuments path”	
	Consortium dinner in downtown Katowice Moodro Restaurant, Katowice, Dobrowolskiego 1a, 40-205	

3.3 Agenda Friday, 27th April – ClairCity Internal Meeting Part 2

9.00	Opening of the Day	
WP update and briefing for External Advisory Board (Chaired by Jim Longhurst)		
9.00 – 9.20	Technical Review Update: Key challenges ahead	Hans Bolscher Enda Hayes
9.20 – 9.40	WP2 update + Q&A	Laura Fogg-Rogers Svein Knudsen
9.40 – 10.00	WP3 update + Q&A	Enda Hayes, Olav ten Bosch
10.00 – 10.20	WP4 update + Q&A	Eva Csobod
10.20 – 10.40	WP5 update + Q&A	Kris Vanherle Vera Rodrigues
10.40 – 11.00	WP6 update + Q&A	Stephan Slingerland
11.00 – 11.20	WP7 update + Q&A	Svein Knudsen
11.20 – 11.40	Panel discussion	
11.40 – 12.00	<i>Coffee & tea break</i>	
Work Packages time		
12.00 – 13.00	<p>WP7 Scenarios (Svein Knudsen and Enda Hayes to lead)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Bringing evidence together through stakeholder dialogue workshop (Baseline reports, Delphi, MLW, Game)</i> • <i>Defining scenarios – number of scenarios, scales of scenarios</i> • <i>Scenario report – number of scenarios, inter-WP communication, number of scenarios etc</i> 	<p><i>Partners not involved in Scenarios discussion may use this time for parallel meetings.</i></p> <p><i>Detailed WP Discussions (to be arranged by WP leads)</i></p>
13.00 – 14.00	<i>Lunch break</i>	
14.00 – 15.00	<p>WP3/5/6 Impact and Policy Packages (Kris Vanherle and Stephan Slingerland to lead)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Impact report – visualisation of results (in report and dotmap potential), timelines</i> • <i>Bringing everything together in city policy packages</i> 	<p><i>Partners not involved in Impact discussion may use this time for parallel meetings.</i></p> <p><i>Detailed WP Discussions (to be arranged by WP leads)</i></p>
15.00 – 16.00	<i>WP Session – Detailed WP Discussions (to be arranged by WP leads)</i>	
16.00 – 16.30	Wrapping up the 3 days	
16.30	Conference close	

3.4 Annex - Cities / Regions Knowledge Exchange session (concept)

Goal:

To create a knowledge exchange platform to enable the cities/regions share ideas, challenges and solutions while learning from each other's experiences and from the consortium members with regard to air quality and climate policies, health and citizen engagement.

Format:

- Small groups with two cities in each group plus consortium members. After each question, we will change the groups.
- Four main questions to be discussed.
- One rapporteur to note on flipchart.
- Plenary feedback and discussion at the end.

Questions around four topics:

1. Measuring air pollution and climate related impacts:
 - What are your biggest challenges in measuring and reporting air quality?
 - What are good practices that could be useful for others as well?
 - How do you deal with citizen science and low-cost measuring initiatives?
 - What role does climate impacts mitigation play in the debate in your city / region?
2. Engaging policy makers and politicians:
 - How do you get attention from policy makers, politicians? What works and what doesn't?
 - What is driving political interest: is it meeting the European norms? Or are health or / and city attractiveness arguments to go beyond these?
 - How do you engage with other city agendas – transport, health, spatial planning, energy etc?
 - How are ambitions in the city influenced by regional and national agendas?
 - What is the impact of the personal motivation / interest of the Mayor?
3. Policy communication and implementation:
 - What are the most successful examples of air quality and climate related policies in your city / region?
 - What are the most important ways to frame / communicate city / region policies towards citizens? What works and what doesn't?
 - Is there anything that you would like to implement but don't get political room for? How could you overcome that?
 - Where do you see 'easy to harvest' synergies between air quality and climate policies?
4. Citizen engagement:
 - Are citizens involved in climate and air quality discussions?
 - What are the most interesting initiatives integrating citizens in the air quality and climate debate in your city?
 - Was it helpful/successful/impactful?

3.4.1 *Timing:*

9.00 – 10.30

Round 1 - Measuring air pollution (20 minutes):

Amsterdam – Sosnowiec

Liguria – Bristol

Aveiro – Ljubljana

Round 2 - Engaging policy makers (20 minutes):

Sosnowiec – Liguria

Bristol – Aveiro

Ljubljana – Amsterdam

Round 3 - Policy implementation (20 minutes):

Liguria – Ljubljana

Amsterdam – Aveiro

Sosnowiec – Bristol

Round 4 - Citizen engagement (20 minutes):

Bristol – Amsterdam

Sosnowiec – Ljubljana

Aveiro - Liguria

10.30 – 11.00

Coffee break

11.00 – 12.00

Plenary session to feed main points back into the group

- Per topic (a-d) summary of the key points by the rapporteurs on issues discussed for that topic (per topic 5 min)
- Discussion on the topic (10 min)

4 Extra materials

Save the date invitation for external audiences

ClairCity Conference

Citizen-led Air Pollution Reduction in Cities

25 April 2018
Sosnowiec, Poland

www.claircity.eu

Protecting citizen health: Mitigating air pollution from domestic heating and transport

You are invited to join us for the ClairCity annual conference 2018, held at the Sosnowiec Science and Technology Park, Poland on 25 April 2018.

This year the conference focus is on:

- Understanding the challenges of urban air quality
- Sharing best practice and cutting edge solutions for air pollution in cities

For more information and registration visit bit.ly/ClairCityPoland2018

5 Attendance list

Attendees included a range of project partners' staff, ClairCity External Advisory Board members and interested representatives from further organisations.

ClairCity Conference attendance list - April 25th

Surname	Name	Organisation
Artola	Irati	Trinomics
Bialik	Grażyna	Senior City Council
Blaszczyk	Adam	Sosnowiec Town Hall
Bolscher	Hans	Trinomics
Boron	Marta	Institute of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health in Sosnowiec
Borrego	Carlos	University of Aveiro
Bosak	Jan	Sosnowiec Town Council
Byszewski	Zbigniew	Sosnowiec Town Hall (First Deputy Mayor)
Cembrzynska	Jolanta	Institute of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health in Sosnowiec
Chytry	Mirosław	Senior City Council
Cichy	Grzegorz	Town Hall
Coelho	Silvia	University of Aveiro
Cravo	Olga	CIM Região de Aveiro
Csobod	Eva	Regional Environmental Center (REC)
Debiev	Anna	Sosnowiec Town Hall
Diab	Roseanne	Academy of Science of South Africa
Diafas	Iason	PBL
Dunford	Chris	We The Curious
Dyrka	Barbara	Senior City Council
Edwards	Andrew	Bristol City Council
Fogg-Rogers	Laura	UWE Bristol
Fredriksen	Mirjam	Norwegian Institute for Air Research (NILU)
Ghirardo	Carlotta	Regione Liguria
Głogowska	Magdalena	National Contact Point for Research Programmes of the European Union in Poland
Hayes	Enda	UWE Bristol
Heves	Gabor	Regional Environmental Center (REC)
Husby	Trond	PBL
Iwińska	Katarzyna	Collegium Civitas
Jedynak	Anna	Sosnowiec Town Hall (Deputy Mayor)
Jaskuła	Anna	Association of Municipalities Polish Network "Energie Cités"

Kamiński	Przemysław	City hall (deputy mayor)
Kamizela-Baranowska	Ewa	Senior City Council
Karaban	Ewa	Sosnowiec City Hall
Karpiński	Jerzy	Senior City Council
Kewo	Angreine	Denmark Technical University (DTU)
Khare	Mukesh	IIT Delhi
Knudsen	Svein	Norwegian Institute for Air Research (NILU)
Koren	Wiet	Statistics Netherlands
Korohoda	Iwona	Association of Municipalities Polish Network "Energie Cités"
Kossowska-Siwiec	Barbara	Sosnowiec City Hall
Kowalik	Magdalena	Sosnowiec City Hall
Koziak	Jolanta	University of the Third Age
Krakowiak	Ewa	Institute of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health in Sosnowiec
Kurek	Jolanta	Institute of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health in Sosnowiec
Kuznik	Jarosław	Rybnik Town Hall
Liu	Xiufeng	Technical university of Denmark (DTU)
Liwochowski	Adam	Sosnowiec Town Hall
Longhurst	Jim	UWE Bristol
Lopes	Myriam	University of Aveiro
Lopez-Aparicio	Susana	NILU - Norwegian Institute for Air Research
Majchrzak	Anna	NILU Polska
Mielzynska	Danuta	Institute of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health in Sosnowiec
Muhamad	Adnan	Hasselt University
Muszynska-Graca	Maja	Institute of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health in Sosnowiec
Napierala	Sławomir	Town hall (mayor)
Nielsen	Per Sieverts	Technical University of Denmark
Nowak	Justyna	Town hall (deputy mayor)
Olko	Wanda	Sosnowiec Town Hall
Olszak	Krzysztof	Zaglebie Smog Alert
Papics	Peter	Transport & Mobility Leuven (TML)
Pastuszka	Romuald	Smog Alarm
Patrone	Angela	Regione Liguria
Peeters	Olav	IRCEL - CELINE

Popit	Sabina	City of Ljubljana
Rodrigues	Vera	University of Aveiro
Scammell	Matt	Bristol City Council
Skiba	Alicja	AGH University of Science and Technology
Skoczeń	Aleksandra	Senior City Council
Slingerland	Stephan	Trinomics
Spaargaren	Gert	Wageningen University
Styszko	Katarzyna	AGH University of Science and Technology
Szlagor	Antoni	Town hall (mayor)
Szuppinger	Péter	Regional Environmental Center (REC)
ten Bosch	Olav	Statistics Netherlands
Thorne	Rebecca	Norwegian Institute for Air Research (NILU)
Tonoz	Mertcan	PWSZ/ PAU
Trozzi	Carlo	Techne Consulting
Turlakiewicz	Beata	Town hall (deputy mayor)
Vaccaro	Rita	Techne Consulting
van Moorselaar	Imke	GGD Amsterdam
van Strien	Rob	GGD Amsterdam
Vanherle	Kris	Transport & Mobility Leuven (TML)
Walczak	Agnieszka	Sosnowiec Town Hall
Wlazlo	Agnieszka	Institute of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health in Sosnowiec
Wykurz	Edyta	Sosnowiec Town Hall
Zaciera	Marzena	Institute of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health in Sosnowiec
Zielińska		Gazeta Polska Codziennie
Zotkowska	Renata	Institute of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health in Sosnowiec
Zralek	Maria	Humanitas University
Żur	Marek	University of Silesia
Zwaniecka	Halina	Senior City Council

ClairCity Conference attendance list - April 26th

Surname	Name	Organisation
Artola	Irati	Trinomics
Bolscher	Hans	Trinomics
Borrego	Carlos	University of Aveiro
Coelho	Silvia	University of Aveiro
Cravo	Olga	CIM Região de Aveiro
Csobod	Eva	Regional Environmental Center (REC)
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Fredriksen	Mirjam	Norwegian Institute for Air Research (NILU)
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Liwochowski	Adam	Sosnowiec Town Hall
Liu	Xiufeng	Technical university of Denmark (DTU)
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Trozzi	Carlo	Techne Consulting
Vaccaro	Rita	Techne Consulting
van Moorselaar	Imke	GGD Amsterdam
van Strien	Rob	GGD Amsterdam
Vanherle	Kris	Transport & Mobility Leuven (TML)
Wykurz	Edyta	Sosnowiec City Hall

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